

METHODOLOGY FOR DEFINING CRITERIA FOR ANALYZING THE ROLE OF THE MILITARY AND THE MILITARY PROFESSION IN CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY: THE FUZZY EXTENSION OF THE AHP METHOD

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Abstract: *Social transformations characteristic of contemporary society have inevitably influenced the military—its organization, missions, societal role, and status. These changes necessitate the continuous transformation of national armed forces. The aim of this paper is to present a methodology for defining criteria for analyzing the position and role of the military and the military profession in modern society. This paper proposes a modification of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method that incorporates the level of uncertainty in decision-making, allowing for a degree of belief that may be less than absolute certainty. The approach introduces linguistic expressions corresponding to the optimality of the compared criteria. To determine the weights of the criteria and the evaluation of alternatives, fuzzy numbers are employed, enabling a more flexible and realistic representation of expert judgment under uncertainty.*

Keywords: *military profession, analysis, decision-making, military sciences, fuzzy AHP,*

1. INTRODUCTION

Given the complexity of the issue, which is influenced by a multitude of diverse factors, their identification and definition are not only desirable but virtually essential. The analytical framework provides a structured approach to data collection and interpretation, guiding researchers toward the appropriate selection of indicators and scientific methods. This ensures that the research process remains coherent and predictable. Moreover, such a framework facilitates the operational definition of the research subject, allowing for the recognition of relevant elements—namely, the societal determinants of the military profession, and more broadly, the internal characteristics of the military organization.

The concept of an "analytical framework" should be understood as a general model that serves to "identify, categorize, and organize those factors considered most relevant for understanding a particular phenomenon" (McGinnis 2011, 167). In the field of political science research, methodologists Milosavljević and Radosavljević propose a "typical cognitive model of the research subject" consisting of six factors, which may also serve, in an adapted form, as a useful model for acquiring scientific insight in the context of this research (Milosavljević & Radosavljević 2006, 74–88).

By applying knowledge from operations research, certain social phenomena can also be quantified, which may facilitate more robust conclusions. At this stage, however, the analysis remains primarily qualitative. The problem context involves considering the future consequences of decisions, the presence of data uncertainty, and the collection of expert insights and opinions. This requires the application of procedures that enable overcoming cognitive biases and the complexity of mental processes.

Within this framework, the assessment of the position and role of the military and the military profession represents a scenario in which it is difficult—often impossible—to identify an optimal solution based on all relevant criteria. This situation is characterized by conflicting opinions, a high degree of uncertainty, and internal complexity, highlighting the necessity of applying multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods. The determination of criteria weights represents one of the fundamental challenges in the development and application of multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) models. This issue has been the subject of extensive scientific investigation and methodological development over several decades. In general, existing methodologies for determining the relative importance of criteria can be categorized into two primary groups: subjective and objective approaches.

Subjective approaches rely on the input of decision makers or domain experts who are directly involved in the decision-making process. The AHP, developed by Saaty (1980), is one of the most widely applied pairwise comparison methods and employs a nine-point scale to assess the relative importance of criteria. In this paper, AHP was modified using fuzzy numbers, resulting in the Fuzzy AHP (FAHP) method, which was then applied to calculate the weight coefficients of the criteria. In order to achieve a higher level of accuracy and to minimize the influence of subjectivity and inconsistency, the significance of the criteria in this study will be evaluated by multiple decision-makers (experts) from the same professional field. Following the initial assessment, the obtained evaluations will be adjusted by taking into account the normalized values of each participant's individual level of competence. The resulting weighted evaluations will then be aggregated and prepared for further analysis using operational research methods.

2. ELEMENTS OF THE ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK FOR UNDERSTANDING THE MILITARY AND THE MILITARY PROFESSION

The image of contemporary society in the security context, and its transformation from the modern to the postmodern era, has reflected upon the military and its need for adaptation. However, understanding the global social context is still not sufficient for fully grasping the role and position of the military in contemporary society—and by extension, the military profession.

Therefore, among the key determinants of the military and the military profession—which the author of this paper identifies, and which may be considered elements of an analytical framework—are the following: (1) the political system and legislative framework, (2) national culture and social values, (3) historical experience, (4) the economy and the level of technical-technological development, (5) the quality of military education and training, and (6) international military cooperation.

This is, of course, a conditional classification that is not final and depends on the historical period and the region being observed.

The political system and legislative framework (C1) represent one of the fundamental factors in determining the character of the military and the military profession within a given society. National culture and social values (C2) are essential for understanding various phenomena and processes, as well as for comprehending the functioning of institutions and the behavior of prominent individuals and society as a whole. Historical experience (C3) is an indispensable element for perceiving the true role of the military and the military profession in society. Without a profound understanding of the past, it is impossible to fully grasp the present or reliably anticipate future developments. The state of the economy and the level of technical and technological development (C4) significantly influence both the size and the quality of the armed forces (Radojević et al., 2023). In order to assess the role and significance of the military within a society, it is necessary to examine the proportion of national budget allocated to defense. The quality of military education and training (C5) must ensure that the armed forces are composed of officers and soldiers who are not only capable but also willing to defend the state, its citizens, and the shared values of the community (Hornstra et al., 2024). Only such members of the military profession can earn the respect of their society, as well as the recognition of peers from other armed forces—be they allies or adversaries. International military cooperation (C6) is a component that undoubtedly contributes to the reputation of the national armed forces, both in the eyes of partner states and militaries, and within the domestic public sphere (Vukadinović & Milenković, 2024).

In accordance with the outlined criteria, the aim of this research is to formulate new criteria—based on expert opinions and their aggregation—by applying multi-criteria decision-making methods and techniques for determining the weighting coefficients of criteria, including elements of expert competence assessment, while taking into account the specific characteristics of the field of Military Sciences.

3. METHODOLOGY

Establishing criteria for decision-making is a complex and responsible task. Today, decision-making almost always involves multi-criteria optimization, that is, making decisions based on more than one criterion. Various mathematical methods have been developed to address such problems.

To enable a more precise evaluation of criteria, a fuzzy linguistic approach was employed. Fuzzy logic and fuzzy sets provide a mathematically formalized means of representing vagueness, uncertainty, and imprecision.

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a method frequently employed in the field of multi-criteria decision-making. The method is based on decomposing a complex problem into a hierarchy, with the overall

goal at the top, followed by criteria, sub-criteria, and alternatives organized across different levels and sub-levels of the hierarchy Figure 1.

A detailed explanation of the method will not be provided here, as its fundamental principles are well-documented in an extensive body of literature (see Liu et al., 2020; Bojanic et al., 2018). In the context of this research, the method is of particular importance as it will be used to derive the weighting coefficients for the criteria.

Figure 1. The General Hierarchical Model in the AHP

The methodology for determining the criteria will be applied through the following steps:

- Step 1 – Defining the problem and determining the objective.
- Step 2 – Identifying the criteria.
- Step 3 – Evaluating/comparing the criteria in terms of their importance relative to the objective.
- Step 4 – Assessing the consistency of the matrix and calculating the weight vector.
- Step 5 – Ranking the criteria.

3.1. Expert evaluation

The first step of the research involved selecting and conducting interviews with experts in order to evaluate the criteria, with the aim of determining the weighting coefficients of the criteria for the application of the fuzzified AHP method. Expert evaluation, as defined by Milićević (2014:18), represents a methodological procedure for obtaining an assessment of a given problem based on the collective (or individual) judgment of subject-matter experts. A critical step in the application of the expert evaluation method is the selection of experts and the assessment of their competence, as it is essential to identify individuals with recognized expertise in the relevant field—experts capable of conducting intuitive-logical analysis of the problem and providing informed judgments. The group of experts was composed of individuals who, through their professional experience, have dealt with the determinants of the military and the military profession. The task of the expert group was to compare the determinants (criteria) in terms of their significance for understanding the role and position of the military—and consequently, the military profession—in contemporary society. A structured interview protocol was developed and applied individually with each expert, following the principles of the Delphi method.

Table 1. Experts qualification

Description	Years of Experience in			Job Position					
	Under 10	Above 10 and under 20	Above 20	Military Analyst / Defense Strategist	Professor of Military Sciences / Defense Studies	Psychologist Specialized Security Institutions	International Relations and Security Policy	Armed Forces Command	Technology and Innovation Expert in the Defense Industry
Number	1	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
Percentage	17%	50%	33%	17%	17%	17%	17%	17%	17%

The competence of the experts was assessed according to the model presented in (Tešić & Božanić, 2024). This model for evaluating expert competence is based on the calculation of the competence coefficient (K). The coefficient encompasses three assessment dimensions: an objective assessment – K_d, an evaluation of the source of argumentation – K_a, and a subjective assessment – K_s. The overall competence coefficient is calculated according to the following formula:

$$K = q_1K_d + q_2K_a + q_3K_s \quad (1)$$

The competence coefficients of the selected experts are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Competence Coefficients of the Selected Experts

Expert	Assessment Aspects			Competence Coefficient	Normalized Values
	<i>K_d</i> (0,6)	<i>K_a</i> (0,25)	<i>K_s</i> (0,15)		
1.	0,95	0,70	0,8	0,86	0,178534572
2.	0,69	0,80	0,8	0,73	0,151186791
3.	0,91	0,85	0,9	0,89	0,184726522
4.	0,74	0,85	0,9	0,79	0,163054696
5.	0,85	0,60	0,8	0,78	0,160990712
6.	0,73	0,85	0,9	0,78	0,161506708

Since the average competence coefficient of the surveyed experts, both individually and as a group, exceeds 0.5, it can be concluded that the experts are competent (Tešić & Božanić, 2024). The obtained competence coefficients (normalized values) will be used as weighting factors in the evaluation of criteria and alternatives during the application of multi-criteria optimization methods.

4. CALCULATION OF CRITERIA WEIGHTING COEFFICIENTS USING THE FAHP METHOD

Fuzzification of the method was carried out by fuzzifying the scale used for comparing the criteria. The simplest way to fuzzify Saaty's scale is through the application of fuzzy numbers with a predefined confidence interval, that is, with a predetermined left and right distribution of the fuzzy number. In other words, the confidence intervals of the fuzzy numbers are first established, and then pairwise comparisons are performed.

Although various approaches to the fuzzification of Saaty's scale exist, triangular fuzzy numbers are most commonly used in the literature. In our study, we use the model $[x-1, x, x+1]$ for values ranging between "equal importance" and "absolute dominance," where x denotes the value of the fuzzy number with a membership degree equal to 1 (Liu et al., 2020; Ekmekcioğlu et al., 2021). The linguistic terms, values of triangular fuzzy numbers, and their reciprocal values are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Linguistic Variables and Fuzzified Evaluation Scales

Linguistic Term	Value According to the Classical Saaty Scale	Triangular Fuzzy Number	Fuzzy Reciprocal Value
Equal significance	1	(1,1,1)	(1/1, 1/1, 1/1)
Low dominance	3	(2,3,4)	(1/4, 1/3, 1/2)
High dominance	5	(4,5,6)	(1/6, 1/5, 1/4)
Highly dominance	7	(6,7,8)	(1/8, 1/7, 1/6)
Absolute dominance	9	(9,9,9)	(1/9, 1/9, 1/9)
Medium values	2	(1,2,3)	(1/3, 1/2, 1/1)
	4	(3,4,5)	(1/5, 1/4, 1/3)
	6	(5,6,7)	(1/7, 1/6, 1/5)
	8	(7,8,9)	(1/9, 1/8, 1/7)

The task of each expert was to individually compare the determinants (criteria) in terms of their importance for the role of the military and the military profession in contemporary society, using the comparison matrix presented in Table 4.

The data collected through interviews were entered for each expert individually. The experts independently evaluated the criteria, respectively. For the purpose of data collection, interviews were conducted with six selected and competent experts.

Table 4. Comparison matrix

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
C1	1, 1, 1					
C2		1, 1, 1				
C3			1, 1, 1			
C4				1, 1, 1		
C5					1, 1, 1	
C6						1, 1, 1

Determining the Consistency of the Matrix and Calculating the Criteria Weight Vector. Since the obtained comparison matrices must satisfy the consistency condition, two parameters were considered for each comparison matrix provided by the experts: the Consistency Index (CI) and the Consistency Ratio (CR). Both parameters are defined by the following expressions (2 and 3), respectively,

$$CI = \lambda_{max} - n / n - 1 \quad (2)$$

$$CR = CI/RI \quad (3)$$

where λ_{max} is the maximum eigenvalue of the comparison matrix, RI is the Random Index, and n is the number of criteria being compared. The value of the Random Index depends on the size of the matrix and is taken from Table 5.

Table 5. The value of the Random Index

N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
RI	0	0	0,58	0,9	1,12	1,24	1,32	1,41	1,45

Table 6. The obtained values of the criteria weights

	C1	C2	...	C6	Fuzzy geom. mean	Wi (fuzzy)	Wi (COA)	Wi (n)	Rank
C1	1,00 1,00 1,00	1,63 4,53 1,22		1,69 2,63 3,05	1,29 1,88 2,40	0,14 0,29 0,52	0,319	0,277	1
C2	0,22 0,27 0,62	1,00 1,00 1,00		0,76 1,10 1,48	0,60 0,82 1,17	0,07 0,13 0,25	0,149	0,130	4
C3	0,22 0,27 0,62	0,74 1,14 2,16		1,18 1,75 2,49	0,68 1,00 1,52	0,08 0,15 0,33	0,187	0,163	3
C4	0,23 0,29 0,38	0,48 0,63 0,82	...	0,53 0,61 0,83	0,44 0,55 0,75	0,05 0,08 0,16	0,099	0,087	6
C5	0,83 1,29 1,92	1,07 1,36 1,94		1,45 2,99 3,83	1,04 1,50 2,06	0,12 0,23 0,45	0,266	0,232	2
C6	0,33 0,42 0,59	0,67 0,91 1,32		1,00 1,00 1,00	0,55 0,70 0,98	0,06 0,11 0,21	0,128	0,111	5
Σ					4,60 6,45 8,88		1,149		
1/ Σ					0,11 0,15 0,21				

Table 7. Rank of Criteria

	Fuzzy Geometric Mean			Fuzzy Criterion Weight			Criterion Weight	Normalized Criterion Weight Value	Rank
C1	1,288	1,882	2,396	0,144	0,286	0,513	0,314	0,274	1
C2	0,605	0,821	1,167	0,068	0,125	0,250	0,147	0,129	4
C3	0,743	1,117	1,598	0,083	0,170	0,342	0,198	0,173	3
C4	0,442	0,549	0,754	0,049	0,084	0,161	0,098	0,086	6
C5	1,044	1,502	2,065	0,117	0,228	0,442	0,262	0,229	2
C6	0,551	0,702	0,977	0,061	0,107	0,209	0,126	0,110	5
Σ	4,508	6,558	9,138				1,146	1	
1/ Σ	0,109	0,152	0,221						

If the value of the Consistency Ratio (CR) is less than 0.10, the inconsistency is within acceptable limits; otherwise, it is necessary to repeat the evaluation and the previous steps. In our case, the experts

demonstrated consistency in their assessments. These confirmed consistent comparison matrices were then weighted using the normalized values of the experts competence coefficients and subsequently aggregated into a single matrix by summing the values of the fuzzy numbers Table 6.

To rank the criteria, the fuzzy geometric mean of the criteria weight coefficients and the weight coefficients of their left and right distributions was first calculated from the aggregated pairwise comparison matrix. The final fuzzy weight value of each criterion was obtained by multiplying the fuzzy geometric mean value with the reciprocal of the sum of the fuzzy geometric means of all criteria. The crisp weight value was derived using the centroid method (as the arithmetic mean), and the values were subsequently normalized. The final ranking of the criteria is presented in Table 7, obtained by using methods of fuzzy AHP.

5. CONCLUSION

The methodology and the analytical framework proposed in this paper is intended to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the role and position of the military and the military profession in contemporary society. As such, it may serve as a solid foundation for future research on this subject. What is certain is that the future of the military and the military profession will be marked by the need for rapid adaptation to dynamic technological, geopolitical, and broader societal changes.

The application of this modified approach to the case of defining criteria for analyzing the position and role of the military and the military profession in modern society demonstrates that the developed model enables the identification of the significance of criteria from a predefined set. Therefore, fuzzy AHP proves to be a valuable tool in the strategic decision-making process in such contexts. The model not only mitigates the cognitive burden on the decision maker but also supports effective decision-making among individuals with limited experience.

Given these advantages, this methodological framework can be extended to other decision-making scenarios, particularly in situations characterized by varying degrees of subjective conviction among decision makers.

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